

Architectural Character Analysis of Senen Area, Central Jakarta

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Abstract:- The Senen area is quite well known by all circles of society, especially the station, the used clothes market and used books which are the main attraction or generator of the area. Many people considered Senen as a trading area in the past, but now the identity and image of this area is starting to shift. Triggered by the uncontrolled development of the city. The Senen area grows in heterogeneity, making it lose its character and values. Development and modernity are being proclaimed, such as the construction of JPOs and busway stops that are connected to regional nodes, but in its development, the architectural history of the city has escaped attention. There are historical buildings that have not been empowered, the relocation of the area of used kwitang books and the emergence of new buildings which quite affect the visual character of the area. Basically, the development of the city cannot be avoided but the artifacts owned can be maintained and strengthened, through the history of identity and architectural values contained. Proper arrangement, management and coordination within the urban fabric can strengthen the image and identity of the area. Senen is expected to be able to fulfill its function as a place for community service by having intact character values. The method applied in research is exploratory-descriptive as a tool in analyzing character, history and its constituent elements, while the rationalistic-qualitative method is used as a tool in forming arguments or a logical understanding of the results of the analysis.

Keywords:- Architectural Character, Senen Area, Image, and Identity

I. INTRODUCTION

The character of regions and cities is a force that needs to be considered in urban design in Indonesia. One of the problems of modern cities in the world is the phenomenon of growing in homogeneity, losing without character so that it loses its human values. For this reason, cities in the *paradigm of sustainable architecture*, the development of contemporary cities is always directed to form cities that fulfill functions as a forum for citizen services and have character. The presence of historical

buildings is an infinite asset for the city that cannot be ignored as an element marking the history of the city as well as the beauty and uniqueness of the city as well as shaping the character of the city. The city as a collage is marked by the existence of modern buildings side by side with historical buildings that mutually reinforce the character of the city as a continuity of city architecture.

In the perspective of cities and regions. The city of Jakarta in this decade is very *concerned* about the preservation of historical areas as city assets. The existence of historical buildings is integrated in the development of the city. However, in its development, this building was not involved, the building was no longer functioned optimally and exacerbated by the uncontrolled development of the surrounding area, causing the existence of the building to lose its role as a *regional landmark*. Revitalization as a program of preserving and reviving in the context of sustainable cities can be applied to increase its role again.

Exploration of the architectural values of the building and the surrounding area needs to be done in order to find a foundation in conservation. It is known that the area does not have direct harmony with existing buildings. *Do the heritage buildings in the Senen area still have demands that are in line with the function of the area? How the history and architectural variety of the building is able to restore the original character of the area and building. How can building preservation benefit building owners, government and the entire wider community?* Based on the questions above, it can be concluded that the empowerment and return of the character of historical buildings must involve its container, namely the Senen area. The research will move from the initial hypothesis or problem through the analysis of the character of historical buildings and the character of the area to the achievement of the formulation of problem solving and regional development potential, which will be a proposal or recommendation that has value benefits for building owners, government and the entire community.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Architectural Character

The character of an architectural object is a collection or arrangement that is characteristic of an architectural object, and is arranged based on shape, line, color, and texture. These architectural elements are found in buildings and share the elements contained in the inner space and façade of the building. Preservation efforts in maintaining architectural works as artifacts from the course of history, intended to live in the present, can study the style and character of the building (style and building characteristic), then analyze it for the benefit of present and future life. The determination of architectural value is based on future use and development. Through physical-visual (aesthetic, extraordinary, regional image, form-authenticity, and observability) and non-physical (historical, commercial, and socio-cultural roles) criteria.

Smardon (1985), Visual character is strengthened by physical quality through relationships between relations and between visual elements in a city.

➤ Intended Characteristics:

- *Dominance (Visually striking or contrasting objects)*
- *Heterogeneous or Diversity (There are several objects that are visually different and are within one scope or container)*
- *Continuity (Objects are visually continuous with each other)*
- *Cohesiveness (Integrity of the natural or man-made landscape order and free from visual distractions)*
- *Unity (Hamoni is the unity of the whole and refers to the congruence between visual elements)*
- *Sequence (sequence of visual units that go in one particular direction or towards a hierarchy)*
- *Uniqueness (visual characteristics are different from other environments)*
- *Beauty (Impressive, attractive and prominent visual appearance)*

➤ Hamid Shirvani (1985)

The character-forming elements consist of four of them:

- *The height of buildings and city open spaces (skyline) that give rise to the direction of linkage between tall buildings and low buildings, between foreground and background buildings. The visual / display relationship in the environment will unite the growth of new buildings with existing buildings and maintain the character of a city area.*
- *Site coverage that functions as;*
 - ✓ Control building density
 - ✓ Manage air corridors and mass visuals.
 - ✓ Manage the layout of the building and its environment.
 - ✓ Manage the capacity of activity functions within buildings and sites.
 - ✓ Manage and protect the history of the city.

- *Managing building pedestrians as an effort to solve problems through proper and appropriate planning. Pedestrian control also provides improved wind conditions on roads and open spaces below so that their role is quite important.*
- *Sunlight and wind, entering through streets and open spaces, and controlling the height and pedestrianity of buildings that can affect the shape or appearance of the city*

➤ Kevin Lynch (1960) & Kenzo Tange

City image is a physical quality given by a visual system to a place (can be a piece of road) capable of causing a strong image of a place. Creates an impression (imageability) and clarity or ability to read (legibility) in a place. Image or mental image of people towards a place, which is composed of three components, namely:

- *Identity allows people to understand urban images through the identification of objects, differences between objects, and things that can be understood or remembered.*

"Identity is not in the likeness of an object to another, it refers to the meaning of individuality that reflects its differences with other objects and its recognition as its own identity. Identity somewhere within a city is a mental image formed from the biological rhythms of a particular place and space reflecting time, which is cultivated from within deeply rooted by the socioeconomic, cultural activity of the people of the city itself" (Lynch, 1960).

- *Structure, namely the pattern of relationships between objects and observers, as well as objects with other objects in a place, with the hope that observers are able to understand urban patterns through relationships between objects and subjects and / other patterns.*
- *The meaning given by objects or environments to observers, that is, people can understand the meaning of objects, the meaning of subjects, and the sense experienced.*
- *The three components can be realized into objects in several ways, namely:*

- ✓ An extraordinary or great object, through a long introduction to the observer to obtain an overview of the identity and organization of its environment.
- ✓ The object is instantly recognizable, because it corresponds to an imitation composed by the observer.
- ✓ The new object, having the structure of a pattern that already exists in the observer's imagination, "Image" is a form of mental representation of a person.

➤ Mc Clusky (1992)

According to McClusky, visual characters are able to strengthen physical forms that are arranged following the visual aesthetic perception of corridor space to produce a complete space. The visual elements in question are:

- *Color, (strengthens the appearance of form, gives expression to the mind of the human seeing, so that the desired atmosphere and taste can be conveyed)*
- *Texture, (there is a dependence on visibility for the observer, because the clarity of the texture will be different at a certain distance and the perception given is also different. But able to liven up the atmosphere through a characterful display.*
- *Scale and proportion, (The relationship between the size of space, shape and people, because it determines the character of outdoor space and becomes one of the ways observers explore the space.*
- *Visual Perception and Meaning, (the character of the city is shaped by human perception as an observer, Urban design is a physical object, solid, touchable, and part of human fantasy, its existence is able to remind the past, and encourage humans to think about the future).*
- *The influence of moving speed, (Management and arrangement of physical elements through the entrance gate of the city, the moving speed factor is able to create visual quality in a road corridor, because it affects the perception of an observer in receiving environmental information visually in moving conditions).*

➤ *Gordon Cullen & Simonds (1961)*

Gordon Cullen has discussed the visual quality of space and area, along with the theoretical understanding and meaning of a piece or sequence of regional sequences. Including:

- *Serial Vision, The characteristic of a city is formed from areas that can be seen or understood as a visual series, meaning that a city cannot be seen in one point only. There needs to be a process of observation in the Movement. The term "optics" for such processes is described in two groups:*
- ✓ *Existing views (focus on one area only).*
- ✓ *Emerging views (focus on the relationship between one region and another)*

The possibility of improving human life can be through the environment first, both physically and non-physically. In the world of architecture, the tendency to the environment is closely related to space and time. A well-planned environment or area is coupled with a drama or visual sequence that can evoke the emotions of the observer. A series or sequence of visual fragments of the region that changes to form a scenario and hierarchy.

Fig 1 Westminster's Vision Series, Showing an Initial Look to the Climax.

Serial vision according to Simonds, 1961 is a sequence of observations or the flow of scenery to a climax point of the atmosphere or object displayed.

- Subject-object position, can be interpreted as a discussion related to our reaction to the position of our body in an environment, namely awareness of an environment. This awareness will be a visual experience with the state of space both outside and inside. If a city or region is designed based on human movement then the whole area will be easier to understand and enjoy, by playing with the emotions of the observer using emphasis, emptying, openness and scope. According to Cullen, the feeling of people's position is influenced by two factors, namely at the level of the boundary (*enclosure*) and the level of protection (*exposure*).
- The contents and faces of objects, contain the meanings recorded in fragments of the area, and relate to color, texture, scale, style, character, personality, and uniqueness. How a person feels in a place depends on two factors, namely on the level of conformity and on the level of creativity. If all spaces are realized in the same way, it will lead to boredom. But if in a space is realized in a very different way, chaos will arise. In urban planning, you must find a meeting point between the two conflicting patterns. It can be concluded that the framework of the urban fabric must be a conformity, where creativity has meaning. An observer can be influenced by what is seen or the identity of the object being observed. There is a distinction between one object and another, this is related to the level of conformity (conformity) and the level of creativity (creativity). If the level of conformity (similarity) is excessive, there will be a monotonous and boring scene. But on the contrary, if an area has a high level of creativity (difference), it will provide a gap.

➤ *Elemen Pembentuk Kota*

According to Kevin Lynch there are five elements that make up a city including *Paths, Landmarks, Nodes, Districts* and *Edges*.

- *Path* (road network as a means of movement can be highways, railway tracks and municipal utility channels. Path is considered an identity that represents a sense of space because the orientation patterns given are real and free)
- *Landmarks (points of interest)* on a small scale of an area, giving identity as the main artifact most prominent in existence. Something that has a distinctive and privileged shape in an area).
- *Nodes*, (spatial nodes of intersecting directions or activities, such as traffic, stations, airports, bridges. Nodes are also a clear space-forming point because they are easier to remember)
- *District*, (the area or neighborhood that contains groups of buildings and the network of roads and nodes within them)
- *Edges*, (linear imaginary axes that can be seen as paths, edges and interpreted as barriers in dividing or uniting 2 regions in 1 area such as beaches, walls, track barriers for trains).

Fig Elements Forming Urban Areas

➤ *Figure Ground*

Areas have a pattern that describes a congruence between the organization of physical space and the organization of social space. In theory, Figure Ground can be divided into 2 elements, namely *Solid* (building mass) and *Void* (open space).

- *Solid (Block) is Divided into three Elements:*
 - ✓ Single block (There is one mass of buildings in a block bounded by roads or natural elements)
 - ✓ Blocks define sides (mass configuration of buildings that demarcate a space)
 - ✓ Terrain blocks (configurations consisting of a widely dispersed mass collection of buildings).

• *Void (Open Space) Consists of:*

- ✓ Open space in the form of yards, has a transitional nature between public and private
- ✓ Open space in or surrounded by a mass of buildings is semi-private to private.
- ✓ Main network of roads and fields
- ✓ Public parking areas can be in the form of parking parks as nodes that function as green area conservation
- ✓ A system of open spaces formed linear and curvilinear. This type is in the form of streams of rivers, lakes and all natural ones.

Fig 3 Texture of the Mass Configuration of Buildings and Environments

➤ *Lingkage*

The quality and quantity of each part of the city is able to give an overall picture of the city, resembling a pazzel that is interconnected to form one identity. That way there is a need for a liaison between pazzels to help people to understand the visual sequence of the city into a unified whole. Linkage theory clarifies the relationships and movements (dynamics) of an *urban spatial fabric*. There are three approaches to visual linkage, structural and collective will be focused on the elaboration of visual quality (visual *lingkage*) The term visual linkage can be formulated in two or more fragments of cities connected into one visual whole.

- *There are Two Differences in Visual Linkage, Namely:*
 - ✓ Connecting two regions in a neutral and balanced manner
 - ✓ Connecting two regions by prioritizing one region as the primary point and the other as a skunder point.

There are five linkage elements that connect visually in the form of; lines, corridors, sides, axes and rhythms. Basic elements that can form the visual quality of space as a whole, namely: main figure, distance, composition and orientation. Road corridors that can be imaged and have structures that can be seen patterns so that there is a pattern of spatial relationships between observers and observed objects. The criteria for designing a corridor that has a clear structure, namely: Definition, translucent and complementary properties.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In research, exploratory-descriptive methods will be applied as a tool in analyzing character and its constituent elements, while rationalistic-qualitative methods as tools in forming logical arguments or understanding of the results of the analysis.

- *Exploratory-Descriptive Method is a method used to describe or describe existing phenomena or conditions through the search for accurate data either through interviews, surveys, and other scientific works. In this study, exploratory-descriptive methods were used to explore clearly related to the description of the character of the building and its area, as well as its constituent elements.*

Table 2 Parameter Eksploratif-Deskriptif

Exploratory - Descriptive Parameters	
Data Scope	Tujuan Pencarian Data
Architectural Variety (Heterogeneous)	Analyze the existence of historical buildings in the area, to be coordinated into a series of interesting city history.
Urban Fabric Area or Urban Spatial Planning	The elements that are the focus of searching for data in the region in analyzing the urban fabric of the area. Path, Landmark, Nodes, District, Edges, Building mass, Open space..

- *The Rationalistic-Qualitative method is used to analyze data by taking the essence, meaning or value contained in it as a logical idea in proving hypotheses or in solving problems.*

Table 3 Rationalistic-Qualitative Parameters

Rationalistic - Qualitative Parameters	
Data Scope	Data Search Purpose
Identity, City/Regional Image	Analyze urban structures or patterns through the relationship between objects with observers or objects with objects within the scope of the area studied.
	Analyze the meaning or perception given by objects and the environment to observers, especially the public
	Analyze serial vision that is felt directly as a feeling that arises when the survey is conducted.

The differences in 1800-1850, 1897 and 1938 were quite noticeable, from what initially there was only density in the center of Batavia city surrounded by rice fields and small villages, to developing in the south with the new town of *Weltevreden*, continued the spread of settlements owned by traders who penetrated following the main routes leading to the old city center of Batavia.

IV. RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

- *Senen Trading History*

The Dutch government (*Deandels*) in 1811-1816, tried to move the center of the old government to a new city named "*Weltevreden*". This area includes the bull field as the center of the square along with the palace adjacent to the road which is quite wide and crosses to form a pattern (Bull Square and its surroundings). The development is realized by involving the construction of other supporting functions or facilities, including: housing or residential, hospitals, hotels, markets, entertainment venues such as cinemas, theater buildings, and transportation facilities such as Crete stations and tram lines. However, the center of office and trade was maintained in the old city center or Batavia (Jakarta Old Town), but planning did not fully go well because the spread of trade activities began to penetrate quickly in areas outside the old city.

Based on the map, the north is Batavia City (Jakarta Old Town) with a density of offices and trade in red, while in the south there is a new city area (*Weltevreden*).

Peta nomor 17 sebagai Pasar Senen dan nomor 5 sebagai Stasiun Pasar Senen dan bangunan bangunan yang mengelilingi diantaranya; (19) *Waterlooplein*, (25) *Theatre*, (34) *Roman Catholic Church*, (30) *Club Condordia*, (31) *Hertogswed (Duke's anenue)*, (27) *Military Hospital* dekat dengan stasiun passer Senin terdapat wilayah dengan tulisan "Kramat" di wilayah ini masuk dalam kategori wilayah *European and Chinese quarters*. Sehingga dapat disimpulkan bahwa kawasan ini memiliki beberapa fungsi yang menunjang aktifitas masyarakat seperti stasiun term, stasiun kreta, rumah sakit, pasar, tempat hiburan dan lain sebagainya. Memasuki tahun 1900an terjadi pemadatan dengan perkembangan wilayah perkotaan.

Gambar 3. Peta Batavia dan Meester Cornelis, tahun 1897 dari *Guide to the Dutch East Indies*

Perbedaan pada 1800-1850, 1897 dan 1938 cukup terlihat, dari yang awalnya hanya terdapat kepadatan di pusat kota Batavia yang dikelilingi persawahan dan perkampungan kecil, hingga berkembang di wilayah selatan dengan kota baru *Weltevreden*, di lanjutkan adanya penyebaran permukiman milik para pedagang yang merambah mengikuti jalur-jalur utama yang mengarah ke pusat kota lama Batavia.

Fig 4 The Development of the City in Batavia.

Source: Personal Documentation 2023

In the 1900s Chinese settlements began to develop, their existence was quite large and influenced urban planning. It can be seen through the map that the emergence of Chinese villages (*China Camps*) began to increase at some point. Until 1939 the Chinese merchant population continued to grow which was marked by the presence of modern Chinese buildings along the main route of Senen and the surrounding area.

Until 1942 the city of Batavia fell into Japanese hands, a policy change that was quite torturous for traders, because looting and forced labor occurred everywhere. Until finally, in 1945-1947 the government returned to the indigenous people, with the beginning of the "*Jakaruta Tokubetsu Shi*" government changed to the "National Government of the City of Jakarta". But the impact of the changes made the need for government offices, employee homes, and trade industries, skyrocketing the population in 1950, 1,432,085 and doubling in 1960 with 2,910,858 inhabitants.

This situation made the government have to provide enough land for buildings and housing, by freeing up land owned by landlords (Dutch citizens) by buying. Land acquisition was accompanied by the destruction of Dutch heritage buildings. In 1950-1960 development began to intensively occur, the government built a power plant in the Ancol area, the construction of *waterzuivering* in the rubber area, the construction of a reservoir in Pluit, the construction of the *Jakarta road by pass* from Tanjong Priok to Cililitan and continued to Bogor, to the construction of contested buildings such as the Istiqlal Mosque, Hotel Indonesia, Pola Building and so on. In 1961-1975 there was an expansion of the region and made Jakarta the capital of the country, with the division of the region into 5 parts.

➤ *It can be Simplified in the Sequence of the history of the City of Jakarta, Including:*

- The stage of settlement was simple in prehistoric times.
- The stage of settlement was coordinated in the time of the Tarumanagara kingdom.

- The forerunner stage as a trading center city, where Sunda Kelapa under the sovereignty of Pajajaran and Jayakarta became a struggle.
- The city stages the center of trade and the center of power,
- Jayakarta was ruled by Dutch colonialists, changed to Batavia
- The Dutch built the New City Center (*Weltevreden*) with modern urban planning along with complete city facilities.
- Batavia (Jakarta Old Town) only became the center of government and trade.
- Rapid development changed the development plan of the city, *Weltevreden began to be filled with offices and trading shops, the emergence of new markets in the Weltevreden area (tanah abang market, senen market and so on).*
- The stage of power change (Dutch colonial, Japanese until returning to indigenous peoples or the National Government of Jakarta City),
- Indonesia became independent with Jakarta being the capital of the country
- Jakarta is experiencing a surge in population
- The occurrence of land acquisition and destruction of Dutch heritage buildings
- Awakening stage

Jakarta is rebuilding the city and dividing its territory into five regions and striving for economic, military and security improvements to the country.

The Senen area is part of the Dutch government's plan to move the city center to *Weltevreden*. The rapid development of the city encouraged people from various cultures to live and trade in the Senen area, thus it can be assumed that "*Senen has a history and function as a trading area in the past*".

➤ *Architectural Diversity of the Area*

The Senen area has a long history along with the history of the city of Jakarta, starting from the Sunda Kelapa area led by Prince Jayakarta. The beginning of the area was filled with people with indigenous cultures until the entry of other cultures through foreign traders, continued by the arrival of the Dutch to control the area and make this area as the city of Batavia.

At this time trade under Dutch rule became increasingly global, making many immigrants from other parts of the world to explore the city of Batavia, such as; Chinese, Persians, Arabs and so on. The entry of various cultures influenced the architecture of the region, especially the Senen area which has a strategic location adjacent to the new city center "Weltevreden" and passed by the main route to the administrative center of Batavia. From the history of the city it is known that various cultures have

Table 5 Description of Objects Mingled from the Past to the Present, this Shows a Period of Architectural Development in the Area

S No	Legend
1.	Masjid Jagal Senen 1600 Ms
2.	Pasar Senen 1735
3.	Stasiun Pasar Senen 1887
4.	Rumah Kapitan Wang Seng 1920-1930
5.	Grand Theater Senen/ Rex 1920
6.	Badan Penelitian dan Perkembangan Kemendagri 1927
7.	Museum Sumpah Pemuda 1928
8.	Gedung CTC Kramat Raya 1950-1960
9.	Kawasan buku bekas kwitang 1960-an
10.	Gedung Wayang Orang Bharata Purwa Senen 1963
11.	Terminal Senen 1974
12.	Monumen Perjuangan Senen 1981
13.	Plaza Atrium 1992
14.	JPO Senen 2021
15.	Persimpangan Senen & JPO Senen
16.	Senen Jaya 1&2

Diversity is always considered "unattractive" because it lacks commonality and order, but this is not entirely true. The diversity accommodated in one container or environment, shows that the area has high wealth and attractiveness in terms of economic, social, cultural. This is evidenced by the variety of architecture that has inhabited this area through its relics, showing the many enthusiasts from various cultures to occupy this area. The Senen area had experienced setbacks because uncontrolled population density made the area look slum, but this could be resolved through government programs at that time.

Architectural diversity in the Senen area must be excavated and strengthened so that its existence is not eroded by the development of the times, because not all historical buildings in this area have been protected. Historical buildings are a series of valuable and priceless city history, have meaning and role for regional and national identity, and their development is able to increase cultural and economic value for the community.

The following map shows the location of objects that have the ability to strengthen the character of the region, the scope of research is limited to the main routes and intersections in the center of the Senen area.

Fig 5 Map of the Location of Buildings in the Senen Area

Tabel 6 Architectural Variety of Senen Area

1. Butcher Mosque Senen 1600 Ms

This mosque is located on the street of Senen station directly opposite Senen station. The mosque was founded by a trader from Bugis Sulawesi, named Upu Daeng Syarifuddin who died in 1745. Based on information from the mosque management, that this building was established since 1600 Ms. Masjid has a Nusantara style and the existence of the mosque is proof that since 1600 Ms the Senen area has been inhabited by traders outside Java.

2. Vincke Passer 1735

Pasar Weltevreden or Vincke Passer was inaugurated on August 30, 1735 along with the establishment of Tanah Abang Market. The founder of this market and landowner was named Justin Vincke. This market has a long journey and is part of the identity of the Senen area, the existence of the market greatly affects the lives of the people there, becoming the most complete shopping center and stall for traders. It can be said that Pasar Senen is both a generator and a magnet for the Senen area. This market is quite familiar among the public, Because this market does not only sell daily necessities but sells used imported clothes that are quite loved by people today.

3. Pasar Senen Station 1887

It was inaugurated by a private railway company named "*Bataviasche Ooster Spoorweg Maatschappij*" (BOSM) along with the opening of the Batavia-Bekasi crossing on March 31, 1887.

This station is in the style of indische empire which is one of the proofs of the development of architecture and transportation history in the past.

Pasar Senen Station has been designated as a cultural heritage building, currently its potential has been well managed to facilitate the people of Jakarta and outside Jakarta. The existence of Senen Station gives an identity to the area, because Senen Station is a large station with quite a lot of cross lines and has all classes ranging from economy, business to executive.

4. Kapitan Wang Seng House 1920-1930

This house was built around the 19th century belonging to a Chinese captain named Wang Seng, during the physical revolution, this house turned into a special entertainment center for the Dutch military (KNIL / KL). The location of this building is in a Chinese residential area headed by Capitol Wang Seng. Its existence shows the diversity and structure of Batavian society in the past. This is because Chinese people are accustomed to living in groups and forming Chinese villages at several points in the Batavia region.

This building has been protected through colonial style with a blend of Chinese architecture. This is one proof of cultural diversity in the Senen area.

5. Grand Theater Senen/ Rex 1920

Built in 1920 as one of the entertainment centers in the downtown area of Waltevreden, this building is quite large and famous for its time.

Today this building is no longer empowered because of its condition that has suffered damage and has lost its original character.

So that the existence of this building is very neglected even though its location at the intersection / city center actually has an important role in shaping the image of the Senen area.

6. Research and Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs 1927

It was built during the Dutch East Indies government in 1927 as the Van Binnenlands Bestuur Department which was engaged in the police, transmigration and agrarian fields. The building has a Dutch colonial architectural style and is still maintained as the office of the Research and Development Agency of the Ministry of Home Affairs.

The history, function, and form of the building as an office are still maintained so that its existence is able to strengthen the image and character of the Senen area which has architectural diversity.

7. Youth Oath Museum 1928

Originally a residence owned by Sie Kong Lian built in the 20th century, in 1908 this building was rented by Stovia students as a place to live and study, known as Commensalen Huis. In 1927 the building was used by various youth movement organizations, such as Sukarno and other figures. Until it was inaugurated as a female building called "Indonesische Clubhuis or Clubgebouw".

The existence of the building has a history in the struggle for Indonesian independence and the building has an interesting acculturation style, namely Indische Empire and Betawi (Kebaya House).

8. CTC Kramat Raya Building 1950-1960

CTC Building is a trading office that has the same function as the Senen area. This building accommodates export-import activities in the 1950-1960s. The style applied to this building is typical Indonesian modern architecture, which is one of the evidences of the periodization of architectural development in Indonesia. The current building is not functioning optimally and is not yet a protected building.

9. Former Kwitang 1960s book area

The former Kwitang book area was very famous in the 1960s because the books provided were quite complete and the prices given were relatively cheap. Most of these second-hand book merchants are surnamed Chinese, located very close to the intersection of the Senen area.

But now used bookstores in the Kwitang area are starting to disappear, because some of them have been moved to the Senen terminal. Quite unfortunate because the existence of this market is a legendary attraction in addition to the second-hand clothing market in the Senen Area.

10. Gedung Wayang Orang Bharata Purwa Senen 1963

This building was established in 1963, becoming a place for the Wayang Orang Bharata community. The style of this building has led to modernity and has become one of the public art spaces managed by the Jakarta Arts Council. This building is included in the list of Heritage buildings.

11. Terminal Senen 1974

The city bus terminal connects one end of the terminus to the other, although many city bus routes remain terminus. The location of this terminal is directly adjacent to Sasar Senen and the center of Senen Area. Its existence facilitates accommodation and transportation of people who want to do activities in this area. So that the accessibility of the area is quite helped by its existence, but there needs to be special attention for users and drivers of public transportation to orderly traffic, such as: not dropping off passengers or looking for passengers in areas that are not allowed. This needs to be considered because it greatly affects the image of the region.

12. Senen Struggle Monument 1981

This monument is located at the corner of Pasar Senen station, and is often referred to as *the "Monument of Determination of Independence or Struggle Senen"*. The monument was inaugurated by Central Jakarta Mayor A Munir on May 2, 1981.

The monument shows that the Senen region had experienced the peristiwa of Indonesian battles and struggles during the independence revolution, especially after allied warships landed in Jakarta on September 29, 1945.

The existence of monuments has symbolic meaning, identity, history and also functions as *landmarks* in the region.

13. Plaza Atrium 1992

Plaza atrium building is owned by Cowell Development group since 2012, this building was designed by Deton Corker Marshall, PT. Duta Cermat Mandiri and built by Duta Graha Indah. The inauguration of this building was carried out on August 21, 1992 by Wiyogo Atmodarminto. The existence of Plaza Atrium strengthens the visual appearance at the intersection point of Senen which is often dubbed as the Senen triangle, because the shape of the mall that adjusts the angled site emphasizes the pattern of roads and intersections and the functions owned strengthen the identity of the area.

14. JPO Senen 2021

The government is revitalizing city facilities as an effort to build the image of the city and also the feasibility of its users. JPO Senen was inaugurated by Anies Baswedan in 2021.

The visual appearance at the Senen intersection becomes more attractive with colorful shapes and *lighting*, giving a new face to the Senen area. In addition, the benefits provided are quite large for pedestrians because they feel safe and comfortable in the area.

15. Simpang lima Pasar Senen was previously a crowded point and prone to crime, because the lack of lighting under the *fly over* and poorly maintained pedestrian bridges (JPO) increased the chances of crime. But recently the Senen intersection was revitalized and found a new face, *Transit Oriented Development* (TOD) developed in the Senen area facilitates public transportation with its unique appearance is quite interesting to observe.

16. Senen Jaya 1 & 2

Gedung ini baru saja resmikan pada April 2023, gedung memiliki fungsi sebagai pusat perbelanjaan modern terbesar di kawasan Senen. Gedung ini merupakan pasar senen yang telah mengalami kebakaran di tahun 2017 silam, sehingga pembangunan gedung ini menjadi salah satu upaya pemulihan ekonomi bagi kawasan Senen.

Within the scope of research, especially the main routes and intersections of the Senen area, it shows architectural diversity. Based on the results of the analysis of buildings with this architectural variety, they have a value or value to the area which can be categorized as follows:

- The object has an identity similar to the function of the region, namely the trade area.
- Objects have certain stylistic characteristics that represent the architectural period of the past.
- The object has extraordinary, aesthetic and quite prominent in its visual appearance, so it can add value / image of the area.
- Objects have historical links to the region and major events in the past.
- Objects are part of the city-forming elements that have an important role in shaping the character of the region, such as landmarks, nodes, paths and so on.

Through the five categories above, the existence of objects is felt to be able to strengthen and shape the image of the area in the Senen area. The Senen area is able to develop its potential through the coordination of objects that have their own value as an attractive city tourism series. Not only coordination but management of endangered buildings to be re-empowered, so as to strengthen the image and character of the Senen area.

➤ *Elements of the City*

The main road network (Path) in the Senen area stretches from the south (Jalan Salemba Raya) to the North (Jalan Gunung Sahari) and is divided into large intersections that divide into 5 directions stretching between the West (Jalan Kramat Kwitang), northwest (Jalan Senen Raya) and east (Jalan Letjen Suprpto). It is easier to recognize because the intersection of five in this area is quite firm through one building that adjusts the pattern of the site and road, this site is often dubbed as the "Senen Triangle". These five intersections can be categorized as nodes in the region. In addition, the linear road network that is quite long from Jalan Raya Salemba to Jalan Gunung Sahari has one cornered bend, and at this angle there is one building that is quite prominent and gives an interesting impression when observers pass by it.

Fig 6 Main Road Map in Kawasan Senen

Fig 7 Location Map of Landmarks in Senen Area

Landmark or landmark, the Senen area is easily recognized through one building that is quite phenomenal, namely Plaza Atrium. This is because the tread that is owned forms a angled triangle between five intersection. The shape of the curved building at an angle is a pattern adjustment is a characteristic that is easy to recognize, the second *landmark* is the Senen

Struggle Monument, because the location of the monument is on the corner of the street Senen Station which is often found by train users so that the formation of characteristics that mark the Senen area. *The third landmark*, the CTC building because of its angular location, the shape of the building mass and interesting characteristics, became a marker or gate for observers that would enter the center or large intersection of the Senen Area, but the condition of the building was not maintained because the building experienced degradation and vacancy in function.

The next element is the district or area that has something in common, basically the Senen area has architectural diversity, but in one small scope, there is one area that was quite famous in the 1960s, namely the former Kwitang book area. In a block or more lined with clone shops that colonize used books, this shows the similarity of functions in one container. But this area is not as popular as before, because its existence was moved into the Senen terminal and left only a few shops.

Fig 8 Restu Bookstore on Jalan Kwitang Raya

Fig 9 Relocation of used book traders in Terminal Senen

➤ *Building Mass and Open Space*

When viewed from the map of areas with *buildings (solid)* marked in yellow and open spaces (voids) marked in white, it shows that the Senen area has heterogeneous characteristics, with characteristics of diverse building periods but arranged with road patterns as open spaces that are still regular.

Analysis of the mass of buildings that are quite dense with a fairly wide distribution and limited by rivers, roads, railway tracks is a residential area.

Fig 10 Senen Area Solid & Void Analysis Map

While the single block that is very easy to mark in this area is a luxury block located in the Senen triangle. This block contains luxury trading functions (atrium mall); residential functions (oasis apartment, Mitra Oasis Residence, Allson Residence Jakarta); Temporary Occupancy Function (Lumira Hotel); office functions (office shophouses and Cohive Cowell Tower Senen).

While the open space in this area is located in the Senen Station area, precisely the pedestrian entrance. This open space has just been built to facilitate pedestrians who want to enter the station area without having to pass through the main gate of the station. In addition, this open space is available as a public space that can be enjoyed by visitors. In addition, there is a large open space in the monument area.

➤ *Regional Linkage*

Within the limited scope of research covering the arterial path and the intersection of Senen, these two regions can be categorized into two different regions. Primary areas are categorized with very high urban activity centers and high architectural value compared to other regions. This point is in the area of the Senen area node.

While areas with moderate intensity, both activities and architectural values are on a linear path on the Kramat Raya road. The so-called skunder area. The primary area has more prominent characteristics because the elements of its constituent elements are quite numerous and complete, transportation mode facilities are also centered in this region. While the skunder area as a complement to the

characteristics as a gate or corridor that delivers. When the skunder area is connected, it will cause a coherent feeling, both when it will enter the center of the region (primary region) and after leaving the center of the region (primary region).

Fig 11 Linkage Analysis Map

➤ *Trading Functions and History*

The Senen area is included in the *Weltevreden area*, which is a new city promoted by the Dutch government as a city center that accommodates modern city facilities. *Weltevreden* has a governor instance replacing *Standhuis* (Jakarta City), hospitals, military *Kampement*, *Waterlooplein* field (bull field), Senen market, entertainment centers such as cinemas and so on. Seeing the development of the new town of *Weltevreden*, people are encouraged to open their businesses adjacent to the city center. Along the mountain road Sahari to Kramat Raya, it became a strategic stall for traders. Because it is located close to the senen market, which at that time became a traditional shopping center of the *Weltevreden* community.

Until the 1900s Chinese villages began to appear around the city of *Weltevreden*. In this year trading activities began to develop, marked by modern Chinese shops along the main road. The transition of Japanese government to return to Native did not change the daily activities of the people, namely to trade.

Fig 12 Trading Atmosphere in Senen Area

In 1947, the Senen area was built by the government through the Senen phase 1 and phase 2 projects, followed by other supporting buildings. Such as the impression market, senen terminal, CTC trading office and so on. Commercial buildings and offices built by the government or private, in the Senen area are a precision. Because the function placed in the container is in accordance with its designation and is supported by the same past history. In observing the Senen area, which is known as a trading area, it is not only seen from its current practical conditions. Like seeing trading activities in Pasar Senen, shops or malls along the main road. But historical buildings that are silent witnesses to the development of trade areas, such as Pasar Senen, Plaza Atrium, Pasar Senen Station and also CTC Kramat Raya building which had the function of a trading office in the 1950s. Functions that are in line and related to storing past memories that can be retold to the next generation. So that the existence of these buildings must be preserved and maintained as artifacts of the region.

➤ Identity and Image of Senen Area

After following the history of the development of the city of Batavia to the Senen area, there is a conclusion that the Senen area is dominated by traders from various cultures. So that the identity and image formed from the past show that the Senen area is a trading area. The problem that arises in the research is *whether the Senen area still has the same identity and image today.*

According to researchers in observing objects and their environment, the Senen area has a trade corridor that functions as a gate in entering or ending the trade area. Starting from the CTC Building which is assumed to be the entrance to the trading center. After passing through the angled CTC Building, there are a series of shops, most of which are used printing and book shops, the atmosphere of trade as an opening stage to culminate in five intersections that have iconic shopping centers plus attractive city facilities cause admiration for anyone who looks. Similarly, when passing through the trading center to Jalan Sahari, there are tall buildings and market crowds that are starting to run out into small shops. This atmosphere indicates that we are heading towards the exit gate. The Vision series or human observation in enjoying the visual presentation that is passed, is able to provide perceptions or feelings that arise.

Fig 13 Map of Research Areas

• Segment 1

Segment 1 begins with the CTC building, this building is an early marker because of its prominent and angled shape that gives attention to anyone who crosses it. The CTC building is assumed to be the starting point continued by the rows of old shophouses, printing houses and used bookstores that deliver to the intersection of five Senen. The height of the CTC building that is not adrift and continued by twin shophouses with parallel heights and similar shapes, gives a visual impression of trade in the 60s.

• Segment 2

Segment 2 is a continuation of segment 1, where segment 2 contains the core or center of the Senen area. This area presents a large open area with views of the modern city complete with crowded public transportation. The iconic building at this intersection is none other than the atrium plaza, located right on the senen triangle with the shape of the building that follows the tread pattern making this building one of the *landmarks* of the region. Plus recent government programs that revitalize public facilities, including JPO Senen, Struggle Monument, and Pasar Senen Station Park which add value to the city's visuals.

• Segment 3

Segment 3 is a suffix or can be assumed to be the exit gate of the region. This area is marked by the presence of shophouses adjacent to the terminal. The visual appearance provided is not as attractive as segment 1 or segment 2, but visually it is quite representative of the end of the series of old shops in the Senen area.

Based on the results of the analysis of the division of three segments, it can be concluded that the taste evoked from the presentation of *serial vision* when an observer passes through a corridor or city space, greatly describes the atmosphere of commerce and offices in the Senen area.

Based on the results of interviews with several train users, conducted by researchers on January 2, 2023 at Senen station, that:

Table 6 Interview Conclusions

Resource Persons of DKI Jakarta Residents	Resource Persons Outside Jakarta Area
<p>Consider the Senen area famous for used book markets, used clothes, Senen Station and Senen intersection which has a new face.</p> <p>This intersection is still hotly discussed by the community, because the community feels that the facilities presented are quite attractive and comfortable to use.</p>	<p>Consider the Senen area famous for its second-hand clothing stations and markets. Because I met several KRL users who brought their groceries in the form of used clothes from the Senen market, and most of them live in the suburbs of Jakarta, such as Bekasi, Depok and so on.</p>

V. CONCLUSION

A. Area Conservation Strategy

The area conservation strategy is carried out as an effort to reorganize the area to restore the vitality of the area that has declined or develop the potential of the area to increase the value of local economic, social and cultural productivity. There are several factors behind the decline in vitality and image of the region, including:

➤ *Safety and Comfort*

The Senen area is a dense and high trading area for crime, such as looting, thuggery, pickpocketing, brawls and so on. Crime occurs driven by opportunities and also possible places. Many spaces in the Senen area are minimal in lighting and crowds such as unused space under the Senen flyover which tends to be dark. The right strategy is the use of space for public activities, such as small parks with attractive garden lights, or skateparks. In addition to reducing crime, it also adds to the attractiveness of the region.

Fig 14 Bottom View of Senen Flyover

➤ *Facilities and Infrastructure*

Public facilities that do not meet security standards and are misused can endanger their users. One of the cases in the area, namely pedestrians along the Senen station road. Pedestrians have been filled with street vendors and illegal parking, which makes pedestrians have to walk on the highway. Other infrastructure facilities that have been damaged or even do not exist, such as tactile for people with disabilities who have suffered a lot of damage. Improvement of facilities and infrastructure has a broad impact, such as increasing people's interest in walking, beautifying the visual appearance of the area, so as to foster a good image for the area.

Fig 15 Pedestrian View Around Pasar Senen

➤ *Application of Regulations*

The Senen area has a fairly high traffic density, this is exacerbated by road user violations, such as: illegal parking, street vendors selling on the shoulder of the road, public transportation waiting or dropping off passengers in inappropriate places and other violations. The impact is felt quite large so that there needs to be application and supervision of every applicable regulation.

Picture 16. Pedestrian view around Pasar Senen

➤ *Space Management*

Many street vendors are forced to sell their wares in places where they shouldn't. Traders are forced to do this because of the high rental costs that are not proportional to the profits obtained and the lack of open space that facilitates traders to sell. The picture beside is the appearance of the Senen grand theater which has long been empty, the building has a long history of cinema in Indonesia and is a Dutch heritage building. But the condition of the building suffered damage and lost its original character, so its existence is neglected to this day.

Fig 17 Side View of Senen Grand theater

It does not have a supporting architectural value, strategic location and a long vacancy in function greatly affects the visual or image of the area.

The space can be used as a forum for street vendors in the Senen area and there needs to be cooperation from several parties to reconstruct and revitalize the building, so that the use of unused spaces in the Senen area can be useful for improving the regional economy.

➤ *Heritage Buildings*

The Senen area has historical buildings that have their own architectural value, and not infrequently these buildings do not include cultural heritage buildings. Such as the CTC Kramat Raya building, butcher mosque, and so on, the existence of historical buildings in the area is endangered due to the lack of maintenance or maintenance on the building, even though the existence of historical buildings can be generators and magnets of the area through the city's tourism potential. City tourism is not based on the type and number of historical buildings in the area. Architectural diversity, functions that are in line with the history of the region can be an interesting sequence of city history. So that the empowerment and preservation of historical buildings is important in increasing the vitality of the region.

Fig 18 View of Butcher Senen Mosque

➤ *Public Awareness*

The amount of damage to public facilities, garbage everywhere and violations that often occur greatly affects the quality of life in it, especially the image of the area. There needs to be an appeal to the public for environmental awareness and insight related to the history of the region. The lack of knowledge about the wealth of the region makes people less respectful of the environment. So that the community is expected to be active in programs organized by the government in fostering the local environment.

B. *Development Potential*

Map of the research area, that the research was carried out only limited to the main roads in the Senen area and included historical buildings in it.

➤ *Strength*

- The Senen area has historical buildings that will complement the city's history or city tourism, such as the CTC building, Senen station, youth oath museum, Senen market, and so on.
- Senen area has the most complete shopping centers, ranging from traditional markets, modern markets, used book markets, to used clothing markets. Conditions that provide added attraction to the region.
- The Senen area has architectural diversity which indicates that the cultures that inhabit the area have ethnic diversity, including China represented by old Chinese shophouses along the main road, kebaya houses owned by the youth oath museum, butcher mosques built by Bugis traders and so on. Cultural diversity in the region indicates that social activities in this region are very good.
- The Senen area has a CTC building that is considered capable of becoming an iconic or *regional landmark*, because of its prominent shape and rare Indonesian modern architecture.

➤ *Weaknesses*

The preservation of historical buildings and the Senen Area, of course, has a drawback or weakness, including the following:

- The government's attention is less on the environment in the Senen area, because the Senen area still has city facilities that are less crowded and prone to crime. For example, the road along the slaughter mosque to the Senen terminal which has damage to pedestrian paths and is still filled with street vendors.
- There is a lack of good cooperation between the government and owners of historical buildings such as the CTC Building.
- The latest government regulation prohibits the sale of used clothes, even though Senen is in great demand by people outside Jakarta because of its used clothes market.
- Transfer of most of the used book traders in kwitang to be allocated at the Senen terminal. Making it difficult for used book seekers who have to be divided in two places, and reducing the attractiveness of the region.

➤ *Peluang (Opportunity)*

The empowerment of historical buildings and areas, will create opportunities that can provide benefits and benefits for the wider community, government and also building owners, including the following:

- Ease in meeting economic and social needs in society.
- Creating added attractiveness in buildings and areas, so as to bring profits, such as tourists, investors, stalls for MSME players and so on.
- Increase income or income for the government from various sectors such as tourism, trade and so on.
- Empowering buildings with new functions that are appropriate and able to contribute to their environment, will bring benefits to building owners, the wider community to the government.
- Opening new insights related to the history of trade, and the characteristics of modern Indonesian architecture in Senen.
- The ease of transportation accommodation and the main route provides added value to the region because it is easily accessible to people outside the region.

➤ *Threats*

- The CTC building has been vacant for quite a long time so it is estimated that the damage to the building is quite a lot and the repair costs that will be incurred are also increasing.
- The more damage to the building will reduce to the original distinctiveness or character of the building.
- City facilities that are left damaged or even neglected, will damage the image and identity of the region.
- Government regulations that are felt to not provide opportunities for second-hand clothing traders to negotiate and spend their merchandise, make the Senen market, especially the used clothes sales area, empty simultaneously and allow a decrease in buyers in the Senen market will have an impact on the regional economy.

➤ *Srategi SWOT*

- The formation of a team of conservation experts by the government involving the owners of historic buildings as well as the local community.
- Owners of historical buildings can cooperate in determining the appropriate new functions, so that the achievement of economic, social and cultural values is achieved as much as possible.
- The government can pay attention or consider appropriate preservation measures for historical buildings in the Senen area as an attractive city tourism demand.
- Shopping centers and transportation facilities in Senen, must be considered maintenance and maintenance, and developed through government programs.
- The government and all parties cooperate in the improvement and maintenance of public infrastructure, to avoid the risk of crime.
- The government can manage urban space more efficiently, taking into account the visual of the city, the needs of community space, safety and user comfort.
- Forming the character, image and identity of the region can be formed through a revitalization program of historical buildings, elements of urban space and facilities and infrastructure.
- The government and the public can help promote the history of the city, public facilities and shopping in Senen.
- Government policies can be reconsidered according to the circumstances and needs of the local community to avoid conflicts in the community and high crime in the Senen area. Examples of thuggery, prohibition of the sale of used clothes and allocation of used books at Senen terminal.

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